

**AN AYURVEDIC APPROACH IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ALOPECIA AREATA
(INDRALUPTA): A CLINICAL CASE REPORT****Dr. Vishakha Dhiman^{1*}, Dr. Ramanand², Dr. Shubham Shandilya³, Dr Abhisek Malakar⁴**¹Md Scholar, Department of Samhita and Siddhant, RAC Lucknow.²Lecturer, Department of Dravyaguna, RAC Lucknow.³Md Scholar, Department of Dravyaguna, RAC Lucknow.⁴Md Scholar, Department of Dravyaguna, RAC Lucknow.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Vishakha Dhiman**

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ABSTRACT

Indralupta, described in the *Ayurvedic classics*, corresponds to the modern clinical condition Alopecia Areata, characterized by localized hair loss from the scalp or beard region. In *Ayurveda*, the ailment is referred to as a *Kshudra Roga* (small disease) and goes by names like *Indralupta*, *Khalitya* (hair fall), *Palitya* (hair greying), etc., yet it causes serious psychological and cosmetic issues. The *romakoopa* (hair follicle) is obstructed by *Pitta* and *Vata* aggravation, followed by *Kapha-Rakta*. These vitiated *Kapha* and *Pitta* create a favorable environment for *Krimi* (micro-organisms/parasites) in the scalp region, that inhibits regeneration, according to *Ayurveda*. Even while corticosteroids and immunosuppressants are the mainstays of modern therapy, they can have serious adverse effects, particularly if taken for a long time. The *Ayurvedic* concept, etiology, pathophysiology, clinical manifestations, and treatment of *indralupta* are all covered in this essay. Here is a case of alopecia areata that was successfully treated with Ayurvedic medicine.

KEYWORD: Indralupta, Alopecia areata, Patchy hairloss, Hair follicle regeneration, Hair follicle growth, Ayurveda management.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda considers hair (*Kesha*) as a by-product (*Mala*) of *Asthi Dhatu*. Proper nutrition, a healthy lifestyle, and balanced *Tridosha* are all necessary for healthy hair development. When these elements are disturbed, scalp conditions like *Khalitya* and *Indralupta* result. *Indralupta* is a type of *Kshudra Roga* described in *Ayurveda*, which resembles *Alopecia Areata* in modern medicine. It is characterized by sudden, patchy hair loss from the scalp due to the involvement of vitiated *doshas* affecting the *romakupa* (hair follicles).

Among various causative factors, *Krimi* (micro-organisms/parasites) are considered important in the etiology of *Indralupta*. Improper diet (*Ahara*) and lifestyle (*Vihara*) vitiate *Kapha* and *Pitta dosha*, creating a favorable environment for the development of *Krimi*. These *Krimis* lodge in the *romakupa* and weaken the structural support of hair by contaminating *Rakta* and *Mamsa dhatu*.

As a result, hair follicles become obstructed and damaged, leading to falling of hair (*Indralupta*). The aggravated *Vata dosha* further dislodges the hair, preventing regrowth. This *krimijanya* type of *Indralupta* is often associated with itching, mild irritation, or inflammation of the scalp along with patchy hair loss.

Thus, *Krimijanya Indralupta* represents a condition where *dosha dushti* along with *krimi dushti* results in follicular destruction, highlighting the importance of both *Shodhana* (purification) and *Krimighna* (anti-parasitic) measures in its management. In *Ayurveda*, "*indralupta*" is frequently associated with alopecia areata. After receiving the right therapies, hair grows back in roughly 90% of alopecia areata patients. But occasionally, it might result in "alopecia totalis," or total baldness.

CASE

A 18-year-old male presented to the Skin OPD of State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow with a chief complaint of sudden, patchy hair loss on the scalp which had commenced approximately 2 months ago. The patient first noticed a small, round, smooth patch of hair loss on scalp, which gradually increased in size over the following weeks. The patch were itchy, irritating and non-painful, with no associated redness, scaling, or inflammation. Hair pull test performed at the margins of the lesion was negative. Nail examination did not reveal any pitting or dystrophy. Systemic examination was within normal limits.

He denied any previous history of hair loss, scalp conditions, or trauma to the affected area. He had no significant medical history of recent illnesses, fever, or systemic issues. Additionally, he reported no family history of autoimmune diseases, thyroid disorders, or

other dermatological conditions. His medical history was unremarkable, with no known allergies, chronic illnesses, or previous treatments for hair loss. He was not taking any medications at the time of presentation and had no significant social or family history of alopecia or autoimmune diseases.

In this case: A single, well-circumscribed alopecic patch measuring approximately 5 × 4 cm was noted over the vertex region of the scalp.

For objective assessment, the Severity of Alopecia Tool (SALT) was applied, which divides the scalp into top (40%), back (24%), right side (18%), and left side (18%). The alopecic lesion was localized to the top area, involving approximately one quadrant of this region, corresponding to an estimated **10–15% scalp hair loss (SALT score 10–15)**. Based on the SALT classification, this was categorized as **mild alopecia areata**.

SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA OF KRIMIJANYA INDRALUPTA

Dosha	Kapha, Pitta, Vata (secondary involvement)
Dushya	Rakta, Mamsa, Romakupa
Agni	Dhatvagni Mandya → Ama formation
Srotas	Raktavaha Srotas, Mamsavaha Srotas
Srotodushti	Sanga (obstruction), Dushti (contamination by Krimi)
Udbhava Sthana	Koshtha
Vyakta Sthana	Shira Romakupa (scalp follicles)
Roga Marga	Bahya Roga Marga
Adhithana	Twak, Romakupa

LINE OF TREATMENT FOR KRIMIJANYA INDRALUPTA

Nidana Parivarjana
↓
Krimighna Chikitsa
↓
Shamana Chikitsa
↓
Rasayan Therapy
↓
Local Application
↓
Pathya Apathya

Table 1: GENERAL EXAMINATION.

Pulse	76bpm
Blood pressure	124/84 mm of hg
Height	165cm
Weight	62kgs
Respiratory rate	22/min
Temperature	Normal
Tongue	Pallor

Table 2: ASHTAVIDHA PARIKSHA.

Nadi	76/min
Mala	Sama
Mutra	Samyaka
Jihva	Samyaka
Shabda	Samyaka

Sparsha	Ruksha
Druk	Swetabha
Akruti	Madhyam

Table 3: DASHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

Sharir Prakriti	Vatta – Pittaja
Manas Prakriti	Rajas
Vikruti	Tridoshaja
Satva	Madhyam
Satmaya	Madhyam
Sara	Asthi
Samhanana	Madhyam
Ahara-Shakti	Madhyam
Jaran-Shakti	Avara
Vyayam Shakti	Avara
Vaya	Madhyam
Kala	Adan
Desha	Sadharana

Table 4: AUSHADHA.

S. No	Aushadha	Matra with anupana	Karma
1	Saptamrut Lauha 125 mg Giloy Satva (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>) 300 mg Krumikuthar Rasa 125mg Amalaki Rasayan 2 gm	twice daily with honey, before and after meals	Keshya, Krimighna, Raktashodhaka - Detoxifying and improves digestion
2	Arogyavardhini Vati	2 tablet twice daily with honey, before meals	Yakrit-Udar Shodhaka (Liver detoxifier) - Raktashodhaka, Ama Pachaka - Improves metabolism and skin health
3	Manjishthadi Kwatha	20 ml twice daily, empty stomach (morning & evening)	Raktashodhaka (Blood purifier) - Pitta-Kapha Shamaka - Anti-inflammatory and detoxifying
4	Triphala churna	5gm bed time with luke warm water	Tridosha Shamaka and detoxifying
5	Gunjabeeja Lepa (External)	Soaked overnight in curd, triturated and rubbed for 5–10 min over patches	Keshya, Lekhana, Kapha-Vata Shamaka - Stimulates hair follicles and improves local circulation
6	Kanchuk Tail (External)	Applied after removal of Gunjabeeja Lepa, once daily	Keshya, Kapha-VataharaRaktaprasadana, promotes hair regrowth, nourishes scalp

BEFORE

AFTER

Table 5: PATHYA AND APATHYA

APATHYA	PATHYA
Junk, fried, spicy, sour, heavy & incompatible foods	Light, fresh, easily digestible diet
Excess tea, coffee, alcohol, sweets, curd at night	Fruits, green veggies, whole grains, Amla, milk, ghee
Night vigil, day sleep, stress, anger, overwork	Proper sleep, stress-free lifestyle, meditation, yoga
Poor scalp hygiene, sun/dust exposure, harsh chemicals	Regular scalp oil massage, gentle care, protection from sun/dust

DISCUSSION

Indralupta, classified under *Kshudra Roga* in Ayurvedic classics, is a condition characterized by localized loss of scalp hair. It bears close resemblance to *Alopecia Areata* described in modern dermatology. The uniqueness of Ayurvedic understanding lies in considering not only *Dosha dushti* but also *Krimijanya nidana* (microbial/parasitic factors) in its pathogenesis.

In *Krimijanya Indralupta*, improper diet and lifestyle lead to vitiation of *Kapha* and *Pitta dosha*. These doshas create a favorable nidus for the manifestation of *Krimi* (micro-organisms/parasites) that invade the *Romakupa* (hair follicles). Once lodged, they cause contamination of *Rakta* and *Mamsa dhatu*, leading to obstruction and damage of follicles. The aggravated *Vata dosha* further dislodges hair shafts, resulting in patchy baldness. Thus, both *dosha dushti* and *krimi dushti* contribute to the clinical picture.

Clinically, *Krimijanya Indralupta* presents as sudden, patchy hair loss with itching, irritation, or mild inflammation of the scalp. This is consistent with the Ayurvedic description of follicular obstruction and microbial involvement. Modern medicine attributes alopecia areata mainly to autoimmune mechanisms; however, the Ayurvedic perspective of *Krimijanya* etiology highlights the possible role of microbial factors and local scalp pathology.

The Severity of Alopecia Tool (SALT) is widely accepted for quantifying the extent of scalp involvement and categorizing disease severity into mild (<25%), moderate (25–49%), severe (50–74%), and very severe (75–100%).

In the present case, the patient exhibited a single alopecic patch over the vertex region with an estimated SALT score of 10–15%, indicating mild alopecia areata. This assessment is consistent with early-stage disease, which generally has a favorable prognosis, especially in the absence of nail changes, family history, or systemic associations. Early identification and grading through SALT scoring not only provide a standardized method of evaluation but also help in monitoring therapeutic outcomes and guiding treatment strategies.

The line of treatment, therefore, emphasizes a combination of *nidana parivarjan*, *Krimighna*, *Shamana*, *Rasayana* and Local applications which helps to eradicate *Krimi* and restore follicular health, while internal use of *ushadh* ensures systemic purification. *Rasayana* support regrowth and strengthen hair roots.

The concept of *Pathya–Apathya* plays a vital role in preventing recurrence. Light, bitter, and detoxifying diets support *Agni* and immunity, while avoidance of heavy, oily, fermented, and unhygienic food reduces chances of *Krimi* formation. Proper hygiene, scalp care, and balanced lifestyle practices further strengthen the therapeutic outcome.

Thus, the Ayurvedic approach to *Krimijanya Indralupta* not only addresses the symptomatic hair loss but also targets the root cause—*dosha* imbalance, *dhatu dushti*, and *Krimi utpatti*. When correlated with modern understanding, this offers a holistic perspective integrating local pathology, systemic imbalances, and immune/microbial factors.

The combined use of *Saptamrut Lauha*, *Giloy Satva* (*Tinospora cordifolia*), *Krumikuthar Rasa* and *Amalaki Rasayan* works in a multi-dimensional way:

- *Raktashodhaka & Dhatu Poshan* → *Saptamrut Lauha, Giloy Satva, Amalaki Rasayana*.
- Immunomodulatory & Anti-inflammatory → *Giloy Satva, Amalaki Rasayana*.
- *Agni deepana & Srotoshodhana* → *Krumikuthar Rasa*.
- *Keshya Rasayana* → *Amalaki Rasayana, Saptamrut Lauha*.

Together, they purify blood, pacify *Pitta–Kapha*, enhance scalp microcirculation, correct metabolism, modulate immunity, and directly strengthen hair roots, making them highly effective in *Indralupta* management.

Manjishthadi Kashaya plays a vital role in *Indralupta* management by:

- Purifying blood and improving scalp microcirculation,
- Pacifying *Pitta–Kapha* doshas,
- Reducing inflammation and follicular blockage,
- Supporting regrowth of hair through better nourishment of follicles.

In *Indralupta*, *Arogyavardhini Vati* works by:

- Correcting digestion and metabolism (*Agni deepana*),
- Purifying blood (*Raktashodhaka*),
- Pacifying *Pitta–Kapha* doshas,
- Supporting liver function and *Rakta dhatu* poshana,
- Acting as *Kushtaghna* and *Rasayana* for long-term follicle health.

Triphala Churna in *Indralupta* works by:

- Detoxifying and regulating metabolism (*Anulomana*, *Ama pachana*),
- Purifying blood and improving scalp circulation (*Raktashodhaka*),
- Balancing *Vata-Pitta-Kapha* to remove follicular blockage,
- Acting as a *Rasayana* to strengthen hair roots and prevent recurrence.

Thus, it is not only a supportive medicine but also a foundational therapy in *Indralupta* management.

Gunjabeeja Lepa (External) in *Indralupta* works by:

- Stimulates hair regrowth
- Improves scalp circulation
- Activates dormant hair roots
- Opens blocked hair follicles

Overall: Follicle stimulant for hair regrowth.

Kanchuk Tail role in *Indralupta* works by:

- Nourishes hair roots (*Keshya*)
- Strengthens existing hair
- Reduces scalp inflammation (*Pitta shamaka*)
- Maintains scalp moisture

Overall: Follicle protector and hair-strengthening oil.

CONCLUSION

Using Ayurvedic Shamana therapy, the patient with alopecia areata was successfully treated. This case demonstrates the effectiveness of a comprehensive ayurvedic treatment for *Indralupta* (Alopecia Areata). The treatment addressed the root cause of hair loss by placing a strong emphasis on diet, cleansing, and dosha balance. Internal medications and external treatments such as *Krimighna* and *shodhana* helped to regenerate hair follicles, purify the body, and restore dosha equilibrium. This comprehensive approach provides a long-lasting and personalized treatment for Alopecia Areata, proving that Ayurveda can treat autoimmune and dermatological conditions when conventional treatments are not enough. Another important component of the treatment was *nidanaparivarjana*. Thus, *Krimijanya* *Indralupta* is not merely a cosmetic issue but a systemic disorder requiring holistic management. With proper *Ahara*, *Vihara*, *Aushadha*, and *Rasayana* therapy, it is possible to arrest progression, promote regrowth, and prevent recurrence.

To verify the effectiveness of this treatment plan, a substantial number of patients should undergo clinical evaluations.

Patient perspectives

“I noticed a bald patch on my scalp, which made me anxious. After Ayurvedic treatment with medicines and

oils, new hair started growing, itching reduced, and my confidence improved.”

Declaration of patient consent

The patient has given informed consent for the publication of this case study and for the use of clinical information and photographs for academic and research purposes. The patient understands that personal identity will be kept confidential, and efforts will be made to ensure anonymity.

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